

Management of Post Bare Sclera Pterygium Excision Granuloma: Case Studies in A Tertiary Health Care Facility in Makurdi

Chaha Kator¹, Saror Member¹, Ogo Lucy¹, Shember Terhemen¹

Department of Ophthalmology, Benue State University Teaching Hospital, Makurdi Benue State- Nigeria

*Correspondence: Chaha Kator, Department of Ophthalmology, Benue State University Teaching Hospital, Makurdi, Nigeria.

E-mail: katorchaha@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

Background: Granuloma formations are a common occurrence of post pterygium excision using the bare sclera technique. The management of the condition has been challenging to the inexperienced ophthalmologist. **Aims:** To highlight the possible causes of the postoperative granuloma formation in bare sclera pterygium excision and its management options in a tertiary health care facility in Makurdi **Cases:** We report 3 cases of granuloma formation after pterygium excision using the bare sclera technique. **Results:** Three patients were managed during the time period of the scope of this study. Two of the three patients managed resolved gradually and completely using the conservative approach with topical steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. One of the three patients had a Dellen's ulcer which was treated surgically. **Conclusion:** Post operative granuloma formations are a common complication with bare sclera pterygium excision. The cause of the disease is largely unknown but the resolution of the granulomas is usually complete with conservative medical management.

Keywords: Granuloma, Pterygium, Bare sclera, Steroids.

INTRODUCTION

Pterygium is a wing-like wedge-shaped fibrovascular degeneration of the conjunctiva usually occurring in the interpalpebral aspect of the eye ball. The treatment of the pterygium is mostly surgical but occasionally complicated by recurrences, granuloma formation, astigmatism and a variety of other conditions. Granuloma formations are a common occurrence post pterygium excision using the bare sclera technique. The management of the granulomas

post pterygium excision can be challenging both for the surgeon and patient.

In this case series we have tried to highlight the possible causes of postoperative granuloma formation post-bare sclera pterygium excision and the management options available to the surgeons.

Case Report 1

A 30-year-old man presented with bilateral nasalpterygia to our clinic. Thorough work-up was done including the base-line laboratory investigations like the

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full blood count, retroviral screening test and fasting blood sugar were done and revealed no abnormalities. He was slated for bare-scleral pterygium excision with topical 5-Fluorouracil application. He was placed on 6-hourly steroid-antibiotic combination with systemic Diclofenac 50mg b.i.d. and discharged home. His review 2 weeks later in the outpatient department revealed a hyperemic nodular swelling in the nasal side of the right eye. He was advised to increase the frequency of the steroid-antibiotic combination eye drops to 2-hourly. His review at 8 weeks revealed a complete regression of the sessile mass.

Figure 1

Case Report -2

A 35 year old female presented to us with nasal pterygium in the left eye. After thorough work-up, she had bare-scleral pterygium excision with 5-Fluorouracil topical application using Weck cells for 4 minutes and irrigating with 15 ml of 0.9% Normal Saline. Postoperatively, she was placed on topical 6-hourly steroid-antibiotic combination with systemic Diclofenac 50mg b.i.d. and discharged home.

Two weeks later during her outpatient visit, she reported pains, redness and a nodular, sessile growth over the initially bare sclera excision site straddling the limbus. The adjacent cornea stained actively with fluorescein dye. An impression of juxta-limbus pyogenic granuloma was made. It measured about 4 mm high and 4 mm wide with associated adjacent Dellen's corneal ulcer. The granuloma was surgically excised mostly due to the cosmetic blemish and the patient was discharged home to continue her topical steroid-antibiotic combination. A week later the ulcer healed and the growth was not visible and at 8-weeks there was no

evidence of tumour regrowth.

Figure 2

Case Report -3

A 32 year old man presented to us with nasal pterygia in both eyes. His laboratory investigations, which included full blood count, fasting blood sugar, and retroviral screening tests, were all normal. He had uneventful bare sclera pterygium excision with 5-Fluorouracil topical application over the bare sclera using Weck cells. Postoperatively, he was placed on topical 6-hourly steroid-antibiotic combination with systemic Diclofenac 50mg b.i.d. Two weeks later he reported with severe eye discomfort and hyperemic nodular growth in the left eye. Our examination revealed a hyperemic swelling of about 3mm diameter and 1mm height in the left eye. He was encouraged to intensify his steroidal-antibiotic instillations and increase the frequency from 6-hourly to 2hrly. Again at 8-weeks there was tumour regression.

Figure 3

DISCUSSION

The term “pterygium” is a Latinized version of the Greek term “pterygion” meaning “small wing. Pterygium pronounced as Tuh-Rij-ee-uhm is an elevated wing-like, wedge-shaped degenerative growth of the conjunctiva invading the peripheral cornea in the interpalpebral area. It could either be found on the nasal or the temporal parts of the conjunctiva, but most commonly on the nasal aspect¹. It is also called the Surfer's eye as it is said to be commoner in surfers². It is a disease most commonly found in the population that is more exposed to Ultraviolet light¹⁻⁶

Pterygia are non-malignant growths that can cause disfigurement of the eyeball, intermittent irritation of the eye and visual blur if not treated early. Pterygium is classified into 5 stages³ based on the progression of the disease as follows:

Stage 0 – Pingueculum/ Posterior to the Limbus

Stage 1 – Tissue involvement of the Limbus

Stage 2 – Tissue just onto the Limbus

Stage 3 – Tissue between the Limbus and the Pupillary Margin

Stage 4 – Tissue Central to the Pupillary Margin

On histological examination, the lesions show several characteristic features: viz. inflammatory cells, neovascularization, remodeling of the extracellular matrix, and a leading edge (head) of altered limbal epithelial cells, followed by squamous metaplastic epithelium showing hyperplasia of the goblet cells, and an underlying stroma of activated, proliferating fibroblasts. These histological features allow pterygia to be classified into three types: proliferative, fibromatous, and atrophic sclerotic^{1,4}

The management of the condition is mostly surgical and the first author to document a surgical approach appears to have been Celsius in 25 AD. The surgical procedures right from then have suffered set-backs including high frequency of recurrence, pyogenic granulomas, etc.^{1,4}

The efforts to reduce these complications have led to a number of surgical modalities and use of adjunctive medications. The surgical procedures most recently in

use that have improved the surgical outcomes include the bare scleral techniques which has a recurrence rate that is unacceptably as high as 30-80%, use of conjunctival autografts with recurrent rate as low as 2-39%, and amniotic membrane grafts with recurrent rate of as low as 0.7%^{1,7}

The Bare Sclera Pterygium Excision Technique started getting popularized in the 1940's and has revolutionized pterygium surgery a great deal. During this procedure the pterygium head or apex is carefully removed from the cornea and dissected posteriorly towards the horizontal recti muscles. The Tenon's capsule is dissected off the sclera exposing the bare surface of the sclera. The author prefers to lift the body of the pterygium together with the apex and apply a gentle pull from the cornea with a beautiful peeling off of the entire pterygium, after which the degenerative, fibrosed tissues under the conjunctiva together with the Tenon's capsule and the head of the pterygium is excised. The sclera is scraped of the all tissues with the scalpel blade, leaving the clear white sclera about 2-3mm from the limbus. No suturing is done. Others use sutures to attach the conjunctiva to the sclera^{1,8,9} Bare sclera technique seems to have more recurrences than the other modalities of pterygium surgeries.^{8,9}

Granuloma formations are a fairly common complication of the bare sclera pterygium excision surgery as well as other surgical modalities^{9,10} and a sure indication of a possible recurrence. Excessive handling of the conjunctival and scleral tissues is thought to be a possible trigger factor for the formation of pyogenic granulomas⁴. In an effort to mitigate the problem of granulomas and recurrences post pterygium surgery, some studies have found granulomas more common in bare sclera pterygium excision and Amniotic Membrane Transplants (AMT) than in Conjunctival Autografts^{4,7,10} and therefore encouraged the use of conjunctival autografts rather than other modalities.

Pyogenic granulomas were originally described by Poncet and Dor in 1897^{11,12}. The term is a misnomer since it contains neither the inflammatory (purulent) exudate nor the typical epithelioid giant cell reaction characteristic of granulomatous inflammation. They are

lesions composed of granulation tissue similar to that seen in wound healing. Granulation tissue consists of proliferating connective tissue (fibroblasts and fibrocytes) and newly formed capillary channels. Acute and chronic inflammatory cells are often interspersed between the fibrovascular elements^{4,12}.

Histologically, a granuloma is a severe inflammatory reaction usually as a result of trauma either surgical or accidental. There is associated severe vaso-proliferation with granulation tissue infiltrations.

Granulomas are commoner post injuries (surgical and non-surgical), pregnant women, children and young adults¹³. In our series, all the patients were in between the ages of 30 and 35 years.

The modalities of granuloma treatment abound including surgical and non-surgical modalities. Surgical modalities include cryotherapy, curettage or scrapping, laser treatment and surgical excision. The non-surgical conservative modalities include topical application of timolol, topical frequent application of steroids, topical application of phenols, Trichloroacetic acid (TCA) and topical application of silver nitrate.¹³

In our case series, all the 3 cases of post-ptyerygium excision using the bare sclera technique that ended up with pyogenic granulomas were successfully treated with liberal use of steroids as seen in the pictures above (fig. 1, 2 and 3) with the exception of the second patient who had a surgical intervention on account of Dellen's ulcer.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

Bare sclera pterygium excision is usually complicated by pyogenic granuloma formations especially in the early adult life and a number of times the tendency is to immediately intervene surgically. From our study, it is obvious that once such occurs, enhanced use of topical steroids will mitigate the complication without recourse to surgery. We recommend therefore that first; the bare sclera technique should be discouraged and particularly on patients in their fourth decade. However, if done at all and there is pyogenic granuloma formation, use of frequent topical steroids should be encouraged rather than repeat surgery.

Secondly, other techniques of pterygium excision should be encouraged among the ophthalmologists for instance conjunctival autograft and amniotic membrane transplant, with adjuvant treatment as they have fewer recurrence rates.

Study Limitations

The number of cases reported on in this study cannot allow us to be categorical with our conclusions hence the need for a study on a larger sample size.

Disclosure

The authors report no conflicts of interest in this work.

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